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**REVIVING INTEREST IN HERBAL MEDICINES:
MARKETING ISSUES AMONG RURAL HEALTH CARE ADVOCATES**

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Abstract

This study intended to surface how rural health care advocates promote the use of the herbal medicines (pharmacognosy) recognized by the Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care (PITAHC), an attached agency of the Department of Health (DOH). Using an interview guide, the researchers sought out medical doctors and pharmacists who were interviewed regarding the spatial, temporal, procedural, and financial components of marketing, as well as to surface reassuring and restraining circumstances experienced by the informants in the promotion of herbal medicines. Results showed that medical doctors and pharmacists conduct counselling and promotion within the confines of their workplaces and only within working hours. Medical doctors promote the use of herbal medicines through prescription while pharmacists do so through dispensing of these medicines. In the financial aspect of promoting herbal medicines, medical doctors and pharmacists receive no compensation, monetary or otherwise.

Keywords: pharmacognosy, marketing strategies, wellness

INTRODUCTION

For centuries now, civilizations have trusted the efficacy of herbal medicines to cure the slightest of fevers and coughs to the seriousness of central nervous system disorders. Way before synthetic drugs came into being, traditional healers in Mesoamerica and in the ancient Mayan culture resorted to several herbs that have been used to address ethnomedical concerns (Castañeda et al, 2022), proving that traditional medicine has a long history; it being the aggregate knowledge, skill, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences native to various cultures, whether founded or not, used to maintain health as well as to prevent, diagnose, improve, or treat physical and mental illness (<https://www.who.int>). In the Philippines, folkloric use of herbal plants by in the ancient times has been handed from one generation to another and considered as part of intangible culture (Tupas and Guido, 2021 and <https://pitahc.gov.ph/>).

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The use of herbal medicine, as one element of complementary and alternative medicine, is increasing worldwide (Welz et al, 2018). The United Nations (UN), through the World Health Organization (WHO) Global Centre for Traditional Medicine, is pushing for the promotion of herbal medicines as a valid, legitimate, and accepted mode of promoting and maintaining wellness, as well as preventing illnesses (<https://who.int>).

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared that the annual demand for medicinal plants is US\$ 14 billion, and is expected to reach the US\$ 5 trillion mark in 25 years or so. The Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) estimates that the export market value of natural health products in the Philippines to be around US\$ 153 million in as early as 2011. Moreover, there is a foreseen rapid growth in the demand for medicinal plants, foods, and personal care products, including cosmetics and home care (Zarsuelo M-AM, Zordilla ZD, Anacio, 2018).

RRL and RS on The Traditional and Alternative Medicine Act (TAMA) of 1997

The creation of the Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care (PITAHC, created by legislation through Republic Act 8423, otherwise known as the Traditional and Alternative Medicine Act [TAMA] of 1997) . PITAHC was created with the objective of improving the quality and delivery of health care services to Filipinos by integrating traditional and alternative health care into the national health care delivery system. Our goal is also to position T&CM (traditional and complementary medicine) as a legitimate field of medicine. (<https://doh.gov.ph> and <https://pitahc.gov.ph>),

RRL and RS on Medicinal Plants in the Philippines

Through the PITAHC, the (DOH) circulated a list of the ten Philippine medicinal plants comprising of the following: Akapulko (*Cassia alata*), Ampalaya (*Momordica charantia*), Bawang (*Allium sativum*), Bayabas (*Psidium guajava*), Lagundi (*Vitex negundo*), Niyog-niyogan (*Quisqualis indica L.*), Sambong (*Blumea balsamifera*), Tsaang Gubat (*Ehretia microphylla Lam.*), Ulasimang Bato|Pansit-Pansitan (*Peperomia pellucida*), and Yerba Buena (*Clinopodium douglasii*)

RRL on Beneficiality, Necessity, and Practicality of Herbal Medicines

Herbal Medicines are beneficial. Philippine medicinal plants are a valuable but often underappreciated resource with innumerable applications for non-communicable and communicable disease indications. Limited research in this field had long been ongoing in the Philippines.

Herbal medicines are necessary. The WHO traditional medicine strategy 2014–2023 was developed and launched in response to the World Health Assembly resolution on traditional medicine (WHA62.13).

Herbal Medicines are practical. Despite price reductions due to legislations such as the Cheaper Medicines Act of 2008, as well as the Generics Act of 1988, those in the lower-income brackets still cannot afford maintenance medicines for hypertension and diabetes as well as antibiotics (Paris, 2019).

RRL and RS on Marketing Herbal Medicines

A research entitled *A Descriptive Study on the Preferences of Community Members toward Utilization of Herbal Medication compared to Synthetic Drugs in the National Capital Region, Philippines* conducted by

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Marquez, Lingat, Silva, Rodriguez, and de Vera in 2020 discovered that while the Philippine herbal drug industry has seen rapid growth over the years with continued support from the government and from the private sector, there is, at present, just 1% of the total drug trade being cornered by the herbal market.

The research established that positive word-of-mouth, satisfaction, and trust significantly impact loyalty in the herbal medicine market. More importantly, the research indicated that the customers' trust partially mediated the impact of word-of-mouth and customer satisfaction on loyalty in the herbal medicine market (Oppong, Gyawu, and Yawson, (2021).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

The diagram above shows the connection among the selected variables in promoting herbal medication by medical practitioners. In a study conducted by Saquing (2021) on festival management, several variables were posited to better understand the concept of events organization. In this study, 4 variables are borrowed, in an attempt to have a clearer understanding on how health care advocates promote herbal medication.

The spatial variable refers to the locus of promoting pharmacognosy happens. It basically answers the question: Where does promoting the use of herbal medicines take place?

The Temporal Variable refers to the time of promotion. When do the health care advocates promote the use of herbal medicines?

The Procedural Variable the how-ness of promoting herbal medicines. The main question to be answered in this aspect is: How are herbal medicines promoted?

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The Financial Variable speaks of the how-much-ness of encouraging patients to resort to herbal medication. The principal question to be answered is: How much does it cost for medical doctors and pharmacists to convince people to use herbal medicines?

Research Paradigm

Figure 2. Research Paradigm

Figure 2 shows the flow of the study, where the researchers shall first discuss the variables of promoting herbal medicines by determining its spatial, temporal, procedural, and financial aspects. This will be connected to the reassuring and restraining factors towards promotion of the same. In doing both of the above, it is the intention of this study to present how to best awaken among the rural areas the interest in resorting to herbal medications.

Statement of Objectives

That herbal medicines take only 1% of the drug industry sets off a red flag in more aspects than one, as it has to be considered that despite support from the public and private sectors, despite efforts done in research and development, the admitted issue of the necessity, beneficiality, and practicality of using herbal medicines, there are only a few Filipinos who actually take herbal medicines to alleviate their bodily pains (Marquez, Lingat, Silva, Rodriguez, and de Vera, 2020). Notwithstanding the fact that pharmacognosy has been in existence for many centuries and has proven to have a strong showing in terms of revenues, still the 1% is a pittance compared to the lion’s share that synthetic pharmaceutical companies have of the current market.

With these in mind, the researchers intend to effect a renewed interest in pharmacognosy by discussing marketing issues among rural health care advocates during the last quarter of 2022 and first quarter of 2023. Specifically, this study aims to:

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- (1) to determine the spatial component/s or locus/i of promotion of the use of herbal medicines;
- (2) to establish the temporal component/s in the promotion or advertisement of herbal medicines;
- (3) to ascertain the procedural component/s in the promotion or advertisement of herbal medicines;
- (4) to discuss the financial component/s in the promotion or advertisement of herbal medicines; and
- (5) to surface encouraging circumstances and challenges noted by the informants in the promotion of herbal medicines.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used the qualitative-descriptive approach to discuss the marketing approaches employed by health care professionals in the promotion of herbal medicines. The informants were interviewed, and asked questions relevant to the intention of this study.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted within the Province of Nueva Vizcaya, a rural area identified as a second-class province based on income classification (<https://blgf.gov.ph>). A landlocked province, bordering the provinces of Quirino, Ifugao, Isabela, Benguet, Pangasinan, and Nueva Ecija, Nueva Vizcaya is composed of 15 municipalities, and is without any city. Current population is 497,432 (<https://cmci.dti.gov.ph>), with only 6 government-managed hospitals and 3 privately-owned hospitals accessible to them. In an interview with a staff of the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), there are around 100 registered pharmacies in the province.

Participants and Sample

The participants of the study are 10 medical doctors and 10 pharmacists currently practicing their profession in the province of Nueva Vizcaya, regardless of whether they practice on a full-time or part-time basis. They may be employed by either in government-managed or privately-owned hospitals, clinics, and/or pharmacies. They shall be selected through purposive sampling and/or snowball sampling.

There are a total of 10 pharmacists-respondents who work in the different areas of Pharmacy in Nueva Vizcaya namely, in the field of community pharmacy, hospital pharmacy, and the DOH-Deployment Program (*Botika ng Barangay*). Of the 10, three (3) are from the community pharmacies, three (3) from the DOH deployment program, and four (4) from hospitals. About six (6) of the respondents are from the government and four (4) from the private companies. 10 doctor-respondents specializing in internal medicine also participated in the study. Five (5) doctors work in government hospitals/clinics, four (4) are

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in private organization, while one (1) of the doctors works in both the government and in the private sector.

Research Instrument

The main research instrument employed in this study is a questionnaire created using the objectives set forth herein as basis. A Table of Specifications facilitated the drafting of the questionnaire which was divided into 2 parts: personal circumstances of the research participant/s, and questions relative to the research being undertaken.

Data-Gathering Procedure

After having drafted the questionnaire, the researchers sought out registered medical doctors and pharmacists and set an appointment for an interview. In the interview session, the informants were briefed of the nature and objectives of the study, and were inquired upon their willingness to participate, including possibilities of the session being documented through audio, video, and photographic recording.

Each recording was transcribed *in toto*, and a printed copy thereof was provided the informant for clarification and certification as to the veracity of the transcription vis-à-vis the recorded session.

Treatment of Data

Transcribed data was analyzed thematically, according to the objectives set forth in this study. Summative or common statements was given premium; and direct quotes were used for emphasis, albeit with the identities of the informants camouflaged in codes. To surface an objective output, readings from related literature and studies was used to either confirm or refute information gathered from the research participants.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, with a cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

There is no conflict of interest in conducting this study.

There is no known risk in the respondent's participation to the study and there is no direct benefit to the respondents either. However, their contributions are considered valuable in the quest to renew interest in the promotion of herbal medicines in a rural area like the Province of Nueva Vizcaya, where 9 hospitals and around 100 pharmacies (government- and privately-owned) cater to the health needs of 497,432 inhabitants spread across 15 municipalities.

An informed consent form was addressed to the respondents. The purpose and significance of the study were discussed, and, to secure the privacy and confidentiality, informants were assigned codes instead of using their names. Data collected are protected by ensuring that access to all confidential and sensitive data collected are managed appropriately. All data gathered are disposed of in a proper manner upon the completion of the study.

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The study involved the conduct of interviews. The researchers ensured that the schedule to interview the participants shall depend on their convenience in terms of venue, date, and time. The respondents were selected as participants because they are the direct informants of this study. There are 20 informants for this study: 10 medical doctors, and 10 pharmacists, whose participation was voluntary, and may be withdrawn upon the instance of the informants at any time during the data-gathering phase of this study.

Information and ideas coming from various authors are cited throughout the paper using the APA citation style.

Saint Mary's University shall be the sole owner of the intellectual property of the study, with credits given to the authors thereof.

RESULTS

All the doctor-respondents who promote herbal medicines, medical counseling is conducted in their respective offices or in the hospitals they work for. The Pharmacist-respondents also conduct their herbal medicine counseling within the workspace (community pharmacy, hospital pharmacy, *Botica ng Barangay*). However, respondents who works in the deployment program of DOH conduct their counseling at their assigned field and medical missions.

With the existing interest on the use of herbal medicines, it is imperative that patients are aware of their proper usage and application. The consequences of the lack of knowledge of their mode of use, potential adverse side-effects, contraindications, and interactions with other existing medicines and even food is dire. Medical professionals, therefore, have a role on the promotion and counselling regarding the use of herbal medicines. Some of the doctor-respondents indicated that they provide medical counselling typically during working hours only. Generally, the responses from the pharmacist-respondents pointed out that during their working hours with no time of day that they conduct the promotion of herbal medications. Since the flow of patients are erratic depending on the need of the patient there is no established time during working hours that they conduct counseling on herbal medicines instead most of them mentioned that they only conduct should the patient mentioned about options of the medications or the based on the assessment of the pharmacist that the patient can resort to cheaper alternatives or of the patient cannot afford to buy medicines on the basis that the alternatives provide the same pharmacological effects.

Due to the technicality of medical terms and jargons, understandability of the information must be taken into consideration to effectively communicate the proper use of herbal medicines. Most of the doctor-respondents mentioned that he conducts face-to-face medical counselling and translates information in simpler terms so that the patient would be able to understand them better. In the conduct of the medical counseling for herbal medicines, the pharmacist-respondents described it as a normal process that they do. They would describe it such as to receiving the patient's prescription and entertaining their questions about herbal medicines.

In the case of herbal medicines, the physicians who promote their usage claim that they don't/have not received any form of compensation (monetary or otherwise) in encouraging their usage. Based on the

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response of pharmacist-respondents, they greatly implied that there was no additional compensation obtained from the promotion of herbal medications.

Doctors have encountered varying views and experiences regarding the use and efficacy of these herbal medicines. The doctor-respondents noted that if herbal medicines show good outcomes and the patient could still shoulder the additional cost, the use of the herbal medicines as an add-on treatment is encouraged. However, they warned that due to its relatively cheap price and the rampant advertisements on these medicines found on television, radio, and on social media, patients tend to forego the use of synthetic drugs and rely solely on the herbal medicines and the come back later with complications or worse conditions. Built on the cumulated responses of patients as encountered by the pharmacists, patient experience was more encouraging rather than negative. Patients were able to utilize the use of the herbal medicines for the relief of symptoms of their underlying disease. Only a few shared opposing experiences which involves the misuse and mishandling of the herbal medication.

DISCUSSION

Many people possess the notion that, being natural, all herbs and foods are safe; this is not the case. Often, herbs and food may interact with other medications people normally take, which may result in adverse reactions (Hussain 2011). One physician noted that he conducts medical counseling even in the homes of his patients when information about herbal medicines is needed. The pharmacist as a medical practitioner is expected to have (medical) counseling which it involves the explanation of the medication regimen to the patient and entertaining questions from the patient related to the medication which ultimately leads to the promotion of alternative therapy that are research based such as herbal medications. In addition, the workplace provides as an important avenue for queries regarding their medications and discussion regarding the use of herbal medications.

With the surge in herbal medicine sales and a lack of immediate and reliable information available to consumers, it is important for pharmacists to be knowledgeable about these products and have the ability to effectively counsel on their uses and risks (Carr 2019). Initially within the pharmacy setting interventions are done ethically by the pharmacist should the patient asks about options apart from the prescribed discussion on generic counterparts or cheaper options such as generic which have the same impact and the suggestion of herbal medicines. Despite the working hours as the time allotted some pharmacist-respondents mentioned that there are times where they promote the use of herbal medicines outside their working time/area or during accidental meetups with patients or through social media. This primarily is due the ease of accessibility of online messaging thru apps such as messenger or email. Although generally the doctor-respondents conduct their medical counseling only within their working hours, one physician indicated that he conducts counselling even after working hours while another noted that he provides counselling whenever her relatives would ask.

Interest in the use of herbal medicines is influenced by various factors but the prevalent reasons indicated by the doctor-respondents include availability and relatively cheap prices compared to synthetic drugs. Thus, patients are presumed to continue their use of herbal medicines and will require the aid of physicians in providing balanced and objective views to patients who seek information on herbal therapy (Bauer, 2000). Patients who take interest in herbal medicines are further counseled and are given information about advantages and disadvantages (*pharmacological effect, side effects, how to prepare*). They later would let the patient decide whether they would take the advice or vice versa. One pharmacist

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in particular those working in the community setting prefer the use of herbal medicines on the criteria that the patient is far from any pharmacy and that the current condition/illness/disease could be easily managed by the herbal medications. This is of course due to the fact as well that these plants are far more economical and have been proven to elicit the same effects with that of the synthetic medicines. One doctor-respondent communicates the relevant risks and benefits of using herbal medicines and encourages the patient to raise questions if there is need for clarification and/or further discussion. One doctor noted that she only promotes the use of herbal medicines when synthetic drugs are no longer effective on the patient, and she stressed that she only promotes the use of herbal medicines as supportive rather than as primary medication.

In the usual settings additional compensation are marked by the manufacturing companies with high status special compensation the pharmacy should sell about the quota. Others would be given sponsored trips or all-expense paid seminar workshops. This serves as a prime motivator for pharmacists, doctors, and even medical representatives to be able to promote the medicines both natural and synthetic ones. However, this does not apply to the responses gathered, in fact all of the respondents were not able to gain anything (monetary and non-monetary) for the promotion of herbal medicines most especially those who are out in the market. True enough the promotion of other herbal medicines not in any dosage forms is an obvious reason for the lack of any source of additional compensation in which these plants are just free, naturally growing, and readily available.

The respondents however responded that despite the lack of additional compensation for the promotion of herbal medicines they still pursued that there is no need to for it and that the patient's overall health is the main priority. *"Pharmacist does not need to receive additional compensation just to encourage the use of herbal medicines to our patients. It is our responsibility to promote a better health and to deliver effective and safe medicines to our patients by using herbal medicines."* One physician even noted that they do not need additional compensation for these promotions as long as it is beneficial to the patient, and another noted that they only do it anyway if the herbal medicine is supported by research studies.

Moreover, pharmacist respondents in the deployment program (DOH) and hospitals both private government and employ the list of herbal medications (Sambong and Lagundi) that are included within the National Formulary, a compendium of drugs identified by the Government to be present within the hospital setting. (RRL on the mandate) it should be part of the National Formulary.

Physicians stressed that herbal medicines are encouraged only as supportive measures and warned that they might have adverse side-effects to the patient. Some of the physicians shared stories of patients with kidney stones and respiratory infections have improved after utilizing Sambong and Lagundi, respectively. Pharmacists played a major factor in the provision on the use of the herbal medications since the patients were able to converse and validate any misinformation about medicines in general. The pharmacist-respondents retorted that like the synthetic drugs herbal medicines also comes in an array of side effects which explains the need to consult a medical professional should they want to shift their treatment into herbal.

CONCLUSIONS

Pharmacists and doctors conduct the promotion of herbal medicines through dispensing and prescribing, respectively, within the confines of their workplaces. Pharmacist-respondents typically

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dispense herbal medicines in the pharmacy while the doctor-respondents prescribe the use of herbal medicines within their clinics or hospitals. Pharmacists and doctors conduct the promotion of herbal medicine use within their working hours only. Doctors promote the use of herbal medicines through prescriptions to patients. On the other hand, pharmacists promote herbal medicine through dispensing these medicines to patients upon prescription of the doctors. Doctors and Pharmacists promote or advertise the use of herbal medicines at no cost. They do not receive any form of monetary compensation to advertise herbal medicines unlike the case with synthetic drugs. The study reveals that promotion of herbal medicines for use is easy due to its availability and relatively low cost and is able to treat underlying conditions of patients. On the other hand, the study also reveals caveats of promoting herbal medicines where patients have the tendency to rely solely on the herbal medications and foregoing the use of synthetic drugs which, in turn, worsens the underlying conditions of the patients instead of curing them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In terms of the spatial and temporal components, in order to widen the scope of promoting herbal medicines, it is possible to conduct E-consultations through messenger or other platforms using the internet. This enables the pharmacists or doctors to easily provide medical counseling by minimizing spatial and temporal barriers. For the procedural component of promoting herbal medicines, additional modalities of promotion and educating patients through utilization of information technology resources is possible. Frequently asked questions (FAQs) could be posted online or physically in order to promote use of herbal medicines and educate patients on their usage and benefits is possible. This saves the time of pharmacists and doctors that could be used in other value-adding activities. With regards to the financial component, more herbal medicines could be converted into dosage forms (decoctions, emulsions, suspensions, tablets etc.), to increase their marketability compared to their raw form (leaves, roots, stems, etc.). Pharmaceutical companies should then commit costs to advertise the dosage forms of herbal medicines. Surfaced challenges encountered by pharmacist and doctors on the use and promotion of herbal medicines could serve as future topics or areas of concern during CPD Seminars so as to address these challenges and come up with a common ground on the use and promotion of herbal medication. For future researchers, this study could serve as a basis where they could focus on the financial aspects of herbal medicines in pharmacies which could then be used as basis for other perspectives of performance of herbal medicines in the market (financial and non-financial).

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